

Weed Identification using Deep Learning and Image Processing in Vegetable Plantation

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Abstract:

Vegetable plantations have irregular plant spacing, making weed identification more difficult than in crop plantations. Finding weeds in vegetable or plant fields is a topic that hasn't received much attention. The main objective of earlier approaches to crop weed identification was identification. Despite the fact that there are many different weed species, directly. In contrast, this essay proposes a revolutionary method that combines deep learning and image processing technologies. First, veggies were identified and bounding boxes were created around them using a trained Center Net model. The remaining green things that continued to fall out of the surrounding boxes were then classified as weeds. By concentrating just on detecting vegetables in this way, the model may avoid dealing with different weed species.

Keywords — DL , GA, image processing , Weed Identification

I. INTRODUCTION

Green vegetables become more prevalent in our diets as living standards rise, adding to their importance to our daily lives and significant economic value. Due to their abundance in vitamins, minerals, and antioxidants, vegetables are among the foods that are considered to be the most nutrient-dense in the entire globe.

Vegetables are susceptible to pest and disease infestation because weeds compete with plants for water, sunshine, and nutrients [1], [2]. In the event of weed-vegetable competition, the output of vegetables reduced by 45% to 95% [3]. The overuse of weed killer leads to problems or critical in regions with little to no weed infestation and has an adverse effect on the ecosystem by contaminating the soil and ground water [4].

As we are not able to look after specific space for growing veggies. Due to the uneven growth patterns of vegetables and weeds, weed identification in a vegetable plantation is more difficult than weed identification in a crop. Furthermore, the fungicide are been cultivated during the plantation process or feed stages and that is to considered through a proper channel separated.

Identification in vegetable plantations is still in its infancy. Previous crop weed identification methods tended to concentrate mostly on weed identification directly.

Thus, other green items in the segmented image were identified as weeds after applying deep learning techniques to first recognize and segment the vegetable, notably the architecture of convolutional neural networks. This technique can considerably reduce the difficulty of weed detection as well as the size of the training image dataset, enhancing weed identification performance and accuracy.

As we are in the approach to develop an algorithm for the removal fungicide problem in plantations associated with DL and Image . As precise goals that are approached one of the specific goals that are given below:

- 1) Develop a deep learning model that could recognise vegetable boxes that were bounded.

2) Using colour feature image processing to extract and segment weeds that fall outside of bounding boxes.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Deep learning has recently displayed astounding ability in automatically extracting complicated features from photos [11]–[13]. It is widely used as a promising technique for object recognition and image categorization. Deep learning for image detection includes two groups of techniques [6]. Object classification comes initially, followed by the drawing of bounding boxes around photos to classify the object. Semantic segmentation, usually referred to as classifying object pixels, is the second category [14]. Using benchmark deep learning models, Olsen et al. [15] employed convolutional neural networks to recognise weeds in soybean crop photos and categorise them as either grass or broadleaf (CNNs).

III. PROPOSED METHOD

The method for weed identification suggested in this study consists of two stages. In the earliest stages of the study, bok choy is identified using by study of Center net inputs. From bok-choy Images taken and used to train neural networks. Box coordinates are detected using the trained neural network, which also produces associated class probabilities. The second stage involves visually classifying based on fungicide images by segmenting plant boundary ranges based on colour data and a colour index. Using Genetic Algorithms (GAs), the employed colour index was chosen and assessed in accordance with the Bayesian classification error. The proposed method's procedural steps are depicted in Fig. 1.

A. Image Acquisition :

A digital camera was used to capture pictures of bok choy, often known as Chinese white cabbage (*Brassica rapa* spp. *chinensis*). The vegetable farm where the photographs were taken is situated in Nanjing, China, at latitude 3212038.17200N and longitude 11848051.8700E. The photos' original sizes were 3024 x 4032 pixels. Images of bok choy were captured in a variety of settings, including

diverse lighting conditions (Figs. 2a, 2b), complicated backdrops (Fig. 2c), and different growth phases (Fig. 2d).

Fig1: Proposed Flow Diagram

Fig2: Pictures of different conditions of Bok Choy
A. Brightness Low B. Luminoisty High C. Degree Complexity D. Different growth Stages

C. Image Augmentation

In order to increase the experimental dataset's richness the 1150 photos from the training dataset were increased to 11500 images utilising data augmentation techniques. Following pre-processing of the gathered photos for colour, appearance, clock direction, and picture expansion, the information was expanded to depicted in Figure -3.

Fig 3: CenterNet model for detecting

C. Image Annotation

Bounding boxes were manually added to the vegetable in the input photographs with a special piece of inputs called Labelling. Associate Formats are considered in order to train the Center-net. The dataset was used for 80% of the training and 20%

of the testing stages, respectively.

E. Evaluation and Training

A cutting-edge identification of product or object recognition that belongs to the key model. Each object in CenterNet is represented by a single point, and the centres of the objects are predicted using a heat map. By the help of Gaussian kernel and FCN estimated centres are determined for heat map's of high stages.

Since Center Net doesn't require -NMS for processing forwarding. It completes significantly quick recognition than other single-stage detection models. Hourglass was selected as the main architecture for feature extraction in this project. In order to train the network, each ground truth key point is split into a smaller key-point heat map using a Gaussian kernel and focal loss Lk.

Fig 4: Training Process of CNN

IV. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

The need input for the hour glass process photographs as shrunk 512 * 512 pixels. A maximum of 24 epochs were used, and the batch size was changed to 4 in order to further analyse the training procedure. CenterNet model defaults applied to additional settings like momentum, initial learning rate, weight decay regularisation, etc. As this will be experienced with inputs of data sets were established using CenterNet original paper's training approach..

A. Genetic Algorithm:

Due to their parallel search space exploration, GA of community of adaptive search methods based on the concepts of biological evolution and the multiple genes human evolution system, are especially effective at solving challenging

combinatorial lookup troubles without stuck in local optimal. The modulation of 3 parameters and boundary of (255, 255), but the range of parameter T is ([0, 1024] [26]). There are 510, 510, 510, and 1024 possible combinations as a consequence.

To tackle this issue, an effective searching algorithm is required. GAs function well when efficiently utilising acquired data in a previously unexplored domain. GA was consequently selected in this endeavour to create the search engine. The operation of a genetic algorithm is described. Fig. 5: Usefulness for the vegetable's sustained development

Fig 5: Genetic Algorithm

Fig 6: Results the colour of Index

V. CONCLUSIONS

We put forth a method that makes use of deep learning and image processing to locate weeds in vegetable plantations. Two steps made up the algorithm's representation. Vegetable detection was taught to a CenterNet model.

A colour index was established and assessed using Genetic Algorithms (GAs) in accordance with Bayesian classification error to separate weeds from the backdrop. By concentrating just on detecting vegetables in this way, the model may avoid dealing with different weed species.

1) Recognition of fungicide in plant based on DL and image by conducting research and describing a strategy.

2) Develop a brand-new, deceptive optical trick to tell weeds from vegetables.

3) Propose a colour scale to help people in real-world situations tell weeds apart from the background.

Despite only being relevant to organic vegetables, The study's suggested algorithm can be applied to robotic mechanical or chemical weeding. The successful results of the study showed that the proposed method is acceptable for ground-based weed identification in vegetable plantations under a variety of conditions, including variable illumination, complex backgrounds, and different growth phases.

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